

Magnetic field effect in homogeneous medium for triplet born radical ions : a way for assessment of inter-radical distance in intermolecular photoinduced electron transfer[†]

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Abstract : Photoinduced electron transfer (PET) reaction involves excitation of either donor or acceptor prior to electron transfer. The PET reaction might occur in the singlet or in the triplet electronic state of the chromophore. These reactions could be influenced by the presence of internal or external magnetic field since radical ions with free electrons are generated as intermediates. Magnetic field effect (MFE) in homogeneous medium could be observed on exciplex luminescence, however the change is very small as the rate of recombination is very high owing to the singlet spin correlation of the geminate radical ion pair (RIP). On the other hand for the triplet born RIPs the detection of MFE needs confinement of the triplet species because at ambient temperature the lifetime of the solvent cages containing spin correlated RIP in homogeneous solvent is 10^{-10} s whereas the rate of intersystem crossing is 10^{-8} s. It is possible to confine the triplet born radicals by using organized assemblies like micelles, reverse micelles, etc., highly viscous solvents at low temperature or long chain biradicals which help to reduce fast escape and thus retain the spin-correlation between the partners of the geminate RIP. MFE is a composite of diffusion dynamics, spin dynamics leading to intersystem crossing and recombination of free ion formation. The effect is optimized only when the inter-radical distance through diffusion becomes sufficient to make exchange interaction between free electrons negligible retaining the original spin-correlation in the solvent cage. In this review we would like to highlight a few systems where MFE for the triplet born radicals could be observed even in homogeneous media due to some specific interactions other than covalent linking, which also helps to assess the inter-radical distance in such intermolecular PET, which is very rare.

Keywords : Magnetic field effect, triplet radical, electron transfer.

Introduction

Recent research has focused on electron transfer reactions between molecules bound to macromolecular assemblies such as polymer, micelles and biomolecules¹⁻³. In such systems besides the covalent bonding the non-covalent weak interactions such as hydrogen bonding, electrostatic attractions and aromatic ring stacking play vital roles^{4,5}. A wide variety of physical techniques e.g. steady state and time-resolved absorption and emission spectroscopy, especially fast transition optical spectroscopy has been used to determine both the thermodynamics and kinetics of photoinduced electron transfer (PET)

reactions. In this review we report PET phenomena mainly for two systems, (i) $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})(\text{L-tyr})]^+$ (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline, L-tyr = L-tyrosinato) complexes individually with calf thymus (CT DNA) and (ii) dibenzo[*a,c*]phenazine (DBPZ) with simple organic amines, in homogeneous medium.

In PET reactions either the donor or the acceptor is photoexcited prior to the electron transfer. Under such a condition electron transfer might occur in the singlet or in the triplet state. The appearance of the intermediate radical ion pairs (RIPs) and their initial spin states can be detected if a time resolved transient absorption technique

[†]In honour of Professor Jai P. Mittal.

can be used in conjunction with an external magnetic field. Magnetic field effect (MFE) on PET has been studied by thousands of scientists over more than three decades and is still ongoing. The RIPs, formed during PET as transient intermediates, contain free electrons and are susceptible to magnetic field⁶⁻¹². The MFE involves diffusive separation, singlet-triplet spin conversion and geminate recombination or free ion formation of the partners of the geminate RIPs into the bulk solvent. The partners of the geminate RIPs undergo a diffusive separation to an optimum distance where the exchange interactions become negligible and maximum intersystem crossing (ISC) occurs between the singlet and triplet RIPs. Application of an external MF, of the order of the hyperfine interactions (HFI), present in the system, or higher, lifts the degeneracy, generally ascribed to Zeeman splitting, between the singlet and the triplet states and inhibits the ISC. This results in an increase of the population of the initial spin states of the RIPs and is manifested by increased absorbance of the RIP intermediates. Therefore, MFE importantly serves to identify the initial electronic spin state of the RIPs. The importance of MFE on PET lies on the fact that this method gives plenty of information regarding the mechanistic pathway of a reaction that proceeds through radical formation. Moreover it gives an idea about the distance between the radicals formed in solution, their orientation, stoichiometry and also the dielectric environment of the radicals.

The PET reactions proceed either through singlet or triplet electronic state of the chromophore. Pet in singlet state could generate fluorescent exciplex between donor and acceptor in excited state. The magnetic field modulated luminescence change in the exciplex system is very small (~1%) because the rate of recombination is very fast and the lifetime of the geminate pair is determined by fast diffusive separation rather than by singlet-triplet spin conversion. So special modulation techniques have to be used to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio¹³.

On the other hand triplet born RIPs are non-fluorescent in nature and they do not recombine to the locally excited triplet state due to energetic factors and recombination to the singlet ground state is also spin forbidden. Therefore the escape reaction, which yields free radicals, predominates in such cases. Now the lifetimes of solvent cages for non-viscous homogeneous solutions at ambient temperature is $\sim 10^{-10}$ s where as a typical singlet-triplet ISC takes $\sim 10^{-8}$ s. As a result no appreciable MFE is expected for triplet RIPs in such homogeneous solvents¹⁴. In order to create favorable conditions for observing MFE

on the free radical yield, the efficiency of the escape channel has to be decreased and for intermolecular PET reactions, this is usually done by lowering the temperature^{15,16} or using highly viscous solvents¹⁷⁻¹⁹ or organized media^{20,21}. In organized media the RIPs are compartmentalized in the restricted environment and can retain their geminate character for a sufficiently long time so that spin flipping can occur. Linked donor-acceptor systems have also been used to study MFE in the triplet state¹⁰.

However there have been some observations of MFE in non-viscous homogeneous solvents too. Levin *et al.* studied MFE on triplet exciplexes formed through PET from triphenylamines to quinones and ketones in different alcohols and found evidences for hyperfine coupling (HFC) and relaxation mechanism²². Another interesting feature is the maximization of the MFE at an intermediate polarity like that observed for singlet exciplexes. Hayashi and coworkers reported the effect of a large magnetic field ~ 10 T, on the PET reaction of triplet xanthone and 2,5-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone with *N,N*-diethylaniline at room temperature in 2-propanol²³. They found reverted MFE similar to that observed in micellar solutions. Further studies of MFE on PET between phenothiazines and electron acceptors in polar solvents have also been reported²⁴. Sakaguchi and Hayashi suggested that homogeneous solution is as good as micellar solution for MFE experiments from their study with 10-methylphenothiazine and 1,4-dicyanobenzene²⁵. Hydrogen abstraction of triplet benzophenone with thiophenol is also known to show MFE for triplet radical pairs in non-viscous solution²⁶. PET between triplet thionine and various monohalogen anilines were studied in low viscosity methanolic solvents at room temperature in the presence of magnetic field by Steiner and coworkers. The results were explained in terms of Δg and triplet mechanism (TM)^{27,28}. Studies were extended to the methylene blue-*p*-iodoaniline system as well in methanol/ethylene glycol mixtures of varying viscosities²⁹. In this case too the Δg and TM are found to dictate the MFE. Evidence for the triplet-doublet quenching mechanism were also found for the MFE on PET between 10-methylphenothiazine and 4-(4-cyanobenzoyloxy) TEMPO in fluid solutions³⁰. Aich *et al.* observed that increasing substitution can lead to an increase in triplet lifetime of the species. Thus MF effect was observed for 1,4,5,8,9-pentamethylcarbazole-1,2,4,5-tetracyanobenzene but not for *N*-ethylcarbazole-1,4-dicyanobenzene in dimethylformamide solvent³¹. Surprisingly large MFE was observed by Ali

et al. for the PET between 4,4'-bipyridine and triethylamine in acetonitrile. Interradical hydrogen bonding mediated by water molecules was believed to be responsible for such large effects³².

Here we shall highlight the PET systems as mentioned earlier, i.e. copper complex-DNA and DBPZ-amines systems where some non-covalent weak interactions like hydrogen bonding, electrostatic attraction, aromatic ring stacking *etc.* play vital role in maintaining the proper donor-acceptor distance required to show MFE for the triplet born RIPs that are explained purely in the light of HFC mechanism.

Experimental techniques

Besides steady-state UV-Vis absorption (Shimadzu UNICAM-UV-500) and steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence (Fluoromax-3 and TCSPC-Edinburg) laser flash photolysis (Applied Photophysics, Lab series, Model Lab 150, Spectra Physics) was mainly used to identify transient triplets, radicals and radical ions by measuring the corresponding lifetime and spectrum by time-resolved absorption technique. Very low d.c. magnetic field (0.08 tesla) was generated through a pair of electromagnetic coils and the deoxygenated samples were kept in between the coils to detect MFE³³.

Generation of *in situ* linked system in homogeneous medium

In homogeneous medium the electron transfer between covalently unlinked donor and acceptor depends on their

diffusional motion. However the donor and the acceptor can be brought nearer to each other by some steady state interaction e.g. electrostatic attraction, hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interaction *etc.* between the donor and acceptor. Even on photoexcitation the donor and the acceptor might come closer to generate an *in situ* linked system.

Steady state non-covalent interactions between donor and acceptor :

Non-covalent weak interactions e.g. electrostatic force of attractions, hydrophobic interaction, hydrogen bonding *etc.* in the steady state might cause the donor and acceptor to come closer. Under this condition photoexcitation of the donor or acceptor causes electron transfer. The RIPs thus produced remain as geminate due to their steady state interaction and spin correlation is possible between them. Competitive binding studies on emission of ethidium bromide (EtBr) and viscometry reveal that $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2]^{2+}$ (**1**) (phen = 1,10-phenanthroline) is known to bind DNA in the ground state³⁴. Though the mode of binding of **1** with calf thymus (CT DNA) is not conclusive, on photoexcitation with a 266 nm laser light an electron transfer occurs from the DNA base to the phen ligand of **1**. This PET phenomenon is manifested primarily from the quenching of the triplet states of **1** with addition of DNA. Fig. 1 shows the systematic quenching of the triplet-triplet absorption spectra of **1** with increasing concentration of CT DNA and a simultaneous

Fig. 1. Transient absorption spectra of the complex (40 μM) at different DNA concentrations : 0.0 μM (\blacksquare), 40 μM (\bullet) and 120 μM (\blacktriangle) in buffer at 0.6 μs after the laser flash.

increase of a peak in the 550 nm region due to the formation of phen^{•-} radical anion. It might seem confusing that DNA also absorbs at 266 nm region. However the molar extinction coefficient of DNA at 266 nm is $\sim 6600 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$, whereas that of bis-phen complex of copper(II) is $\sim 56974 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$. Therefore, when a mixture of **1** and DNA is excited by 266 nm laser light the probability of excitation of DNA is very much lower compared to the copper complex. The PET occurs from the DNA base, preferably from guanine as it is the most easily oxidisable component of DNA, so the DNA radical cation might be of guanine radical cation^{35,36} G^{•+}. The G^{•+} thus produced undergoes rapid deprotonation to guanine radical. The formation of the guanine radical that appears at 390 nm is not very prominent in Fig. 1. However in presence of an external magnetic field the lifetime of the guanine radical should increase if the PET occurs in the triplet state. Fig. 2 shows magnetic field induced increased yield of guanine radical at 390 nm and that of phen^{•-} radical anion at 550 nm. Thus a prominent MFE is observed in the homogeneous buffer medium for the triplet born radicals.

Now, the question is why MFE is observed in homogeneous buffer medium for the triplet born RIPs? Due to

steady state weak interaction of CT DNA and bis-phen complex, which might be partial intercalation or groove binding, the phen^{•-} and DNA^{•+} cannot remain very close to each other which in turn maintain the optimum distance between donor and acceptor with negligible exchange interaction favoring the occurrence of the MFE even in homogeneous medium³⁷. If the complex is a perfect intercalator then the DNA base radical cation and ligand radical anion should be very nearer to each other and due to the presence of sufficient exchange interaction MFE could not be observed.

Similar phenomena occur if one of the phen ligand of **1** is substituted with an amino acid L-tyrosinato (tyr). Photoexcitation of this new complex [Cu(phen)(tyr)]⁺ (**2**) leads to an intramolecular electron transfer from tyr to phen within it. In presence of CT DNA complex **2** binds to the polymer in the ground state. The driving force of this binding is the electrostatic force of attraction between positively charged copper complex and negatively charged nucleic acid and the hydrophobic interaction between phen ring and the DNA base pairs. The interaction of the complex **2** with DNA can be proved well by competitive binding study of **2** in presence of a known intercalator EtBr by fluorescence spectroscopy using emis-

Fig. 2. Transient absorption spectra of the complex (40 μM) - DNA (120 μM) in buffer in absence (■) and presence (●) of 0.08 T MF at a delay of 0.6 μs after the laser flash. Inset shows the decay profile of the transient at 380 nm in absence (▲) and in presence (●) of MF.

sion intensity of EtBr. The observed decrease in emission intensity of DNA bound EtBr at different concentration of complex 2 is shown in Fig. 3. On the other hand the small intrinsic fluorescence of free EtBr is not quenched

Fig. 3. Quenching of the emission intensity of CT DNA (100 μ M) bound EtBr (4.5 μ M) at different complex 2 (■) concentrations ($\lambda_{ex} = 512$ nm). The intrinsic fluorescence of EtBr is not quenched with the concentration of complex (2) (▲).

on addition of complex 2. This suggests that the complex 2 can displace the inserted EtBr from CT DNA though at much higher concentration than that of EtBr. Thus complex 2 interacts with CT DNA either through partial in-

tercalation or groove binding. Though in case of 2 an intramolecular PET occurs from tyr to phen, however, in presence of CT DNA intermolecular PET occurs predominantly from DNA to phen. Later the oxidative damage on DNA might be repaired by tyr, which is thermodynamically more favorable. In presence of an external magnetic field a prominent MFE has been observed for this intermolecular PET in buffer medium. Fig. 4 shows magnetic field induced increased yield of the guanine radical at 380 nm and that of phen⁻ radical anion at 550 nm in buffer medium³⁸.

Furthermore if the PET reaction for the complex-DNA system is done in AOT reverse micelles (sodium bis(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinate in heptane and water) in that case the MFE is prominent only at a particular water pool size 20 Å ($W_0 = [H_2O]/[AOT] = 10$). At very high or very low water pool size the MFE dies out quickly. Rather the extent of MFE is also less in AOT reverse micelles compared to that in pure buffer medium. As the copper complexes have greater solubility in the non-aqueous medium partitioning of the complex in two solvent systems (water and heptane) lowers the concentration of the complex in water pool and also increases the distance

Fig. 4. Transient absorption spectra of the complex 2 (40 μ M) – DNA (80 μ M) in buffer in absence (■) (black) and presence (▲) of 0.08 T MF at a delay of 0.6 μ s after the laser flash.

between the complex and DNA required to show MFE. This proves that the occurrence of MFE requires an optimum distance of separation between the donor and acceptor.

Non-covalent interaction between the donor and acceptor in the excited state :

The donor and the acceptor could be brought about nearer through non-covalent interactions even after photo excitation. One of the most interesting example of such kind is DBPZ that forms excited state hydrogen bonding with different hydroxylic solvents, although remains insensitive to the polarity of the medium. This makes it a very good sensor for the protic solvents even in an aprotic environment³⁹. On addition of protic solvents the fluorescence peak of DBPZ at 420 nm is red shifted with a concomitant increase in fluorescence quantum yield and lifetime due to the formation of excited state hydrogen bonded species. However, the excited state hydrogen bonding of DBPZ with protic solvents depends both on the size and hydrogen bond donating ability of the solvents. For example, although water has lower hydrogen bond donating capacity than trifluoroethanol, the strongest hydrogen bond donor among all the alcohols⁴⁰, it can form the most stable hydrogen bonded species with DBPZ due to its smallest size with least steric crowding among all the protic solvents that brings it very close to DBPZ. The structure of the molecule is responsible for this peculiar behavior. Dias *et al.*⁴¹ have reported that the 1, 8 protons of DBPZ experience moderate deshielding by the nitrogen atoms compared to its hydrocarbon homologue dibenzo[*a,c*]anthracene (DBA). As a result greater chemical shift for 1, 8 hydrogens were found for DBPZ (9.3 ppm) compared to DBA (8.7 ppm) in the ¹H NMR spectroscopy (Fig. 5). The protons in the 1 and 8 positions sterically interact with the lone pair of electrons of the proximate nitrogens. For this reason bulky solvent mole-

Fig. 5. Structure of dibenzo[*a,c*]phenazine and dibenzo[*a,c*]anthracene and the ¹H NMR values of the 1, 8 hydrogens.

cules cannot interact with the nitrogens and DBPZ remains insensitive to polarity of its environment. However, hydrogen being smallest element can come closer to the nitrogen lone pair. For this reason only those solvents containing hydroxylic groups can interact with DBPZ due to their hydrogen bond donor ability. Thus DBPZ acts as a polarity insensitive hydrogen-bonding probe.

The excited state hydrogen bonding is also evident during PET between DBPZ and organic amines e.g. *N,N*-dimethylaniline (DMA), 4,4'-bis(dimethylamino)-diphenylmethane (DMDPM) and triethylamine (TEA) even in triplet state. The transient radical cations of amines and anion of DBPZ formed due to electron transfer in the triplet state from amines to DBPZ were monitored by laser flash photolysis technique. A prominent MFE was observed for radical ion pairs formed due to electron transfer between DBPZ and amines even in homogeneous acetonitrile/water mixture and the effect increases on addition of water up to its 0.15 *M* concentration in the mixture. Further addition of water decreases the field effect. This observation could be explained only by considering inter-radical hydrogen bonding via the intervening water molecules, (Fig. 6) which helps to sustain the geminate characteristics and hence the spin correlation in the RIPs to show maximum field effect up to that particular concentration of water, beyond of which the spin correlation gets lost and MFE decreases⁴². The occurrence of inter-radical hydrogen bonding is also supported by the following observation. In case of water-soluble amines

Fig. 6. The proposed structure of excited state hydrogen bonded DBPZ and triethylamine. The number of intervening water molecules might be more than one.

like triethylamine the estimated hyperfine interactions from observed MFE is lower than the calculated hyperfine interactions obtained from the electron density of the RIPs. Since the amine is water-soluble its cation can come very close to DBPZ anion through intervening water molecules, which induces very fast electron exchange in the geminate RIP and decreases effective MFE. Thus in this case MFE for triplet born transients in homogeneous acetonitrile/water mixture has been observed due to excited state hydrogen bonding between DBPZ and water.

Conclusion :

At the end we can conclude that MFE in PET reactions can serve as an efficient tool for identification of the initial spin state of the geminate RIPs formed due to electron transfer. The essential features for observation of MFEs are the diffusion, spin flipping and recombination or free ion formation depending on the singlet or triplet spin states respectively of the spin correlated geminate RIPs. If the participating radical ions are very close to each other, the exchange interaction will hinder spin conversion, whereas a large distance of separation between them will destroy the spin correlation and their geminate characteristics. Both the phenomena will reduce MFE. Therefore, MFE indirectly serves as a tool to estimate the separation distance between geminate radical ions and maximum field effect is obtained at an optimum inter-radical distance where maximum spin flipping and consecutive phenomena could take place. Most of the magnetic field effect studies on triplet born radical ion pairs using laser flash photolysis are carried out in viscous or confined media rather than in homogeneous non-viscous medium to enhance the lifetime of the spin correlated geminate RIPs. However it can also be observed in homogeneous medium if the donor and acceptor can be brought nearer by some steady state or excited state interaction.

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